

SPINNING THE WHORL OF THE SPINDLE: MARSILIO FICINO ON PLATO'S MYTH OF ER IN THE *ARGUMENTUM IN PLATONIS RESPUBLICAM*

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Abstract

Marsilio Ficino (1433–99) was greatly intrigued by the questions on free will raised by the myth of Er in Plato's *Republic*. By focusing on his *Argumentum in Platonis Respublicam*, this article discusses Ficino's interpretation of the myth in the light of his view on the faculties of the soul—intellect, reason, the imagination, and the vegetative power—and of how they become subject to providence or fate. Moreover, it will situate Ficino's discussion of the myth within his understanding of the universe as an interconnected organism in which different levels of life are perfectly attuned with one another.

Keywords: myth of Er, Marsilio Ficino, divine allotment, necessity, providence and fate.

1. FICINO ON NECESSITY AND HER DAUGHTERS

Plato's *Republic* is one of the most widely read works in Western philosophy. Its ethical and political concerns, explored through Socrates's indefatigable inquiries, revolve around the questions "What is justice?" and "Is the just life happier than the unjust?" As the dialogue proceeds, the concept of justice is developed at both the objective historical-social level and at the subjective level to provide the basis for an integrated critique of human political structures and the psychological patterns that create and sustain them. But while Plato's treatment of social and psychological factors in the *Republic* is amenable to and consistent with

secular interpretations of the Greek polis, his account of reincarnation and the individual soul's role *between births* in choosing the kind of life it will lead on earth offers a very different perspective.

The *Republic* famously ends with a myth of the afterlife, known as the myth of Er (*Rep.*10.614–10.621). The myth begins when Er, an Armenian soldier, wakes up from death on his funeral pyre and recounts his journey in the other world. For centuries, the beautifully crafted narrative of this tale has attracted and bewildered Plato's readers. Its most intriguing part comes with the description of what happens to souls between incarnations. They arrive at the meadows where their fates are woven into a rainbow-like spindle that extends into the heavens and is held by the goddess Necessity between her knees. Necessity's daughters, Lachesis, Clotho, and Atropos, are also present at the scene, each one on her throne, dressed in white and with garlands on her head, singing to the chant of the Sirens who stand on top of each of the eight circles that form the spindle's whorl. Lachesis sings of things past, Clotho of things present, and Atropos of things to come. From time to time, they help turn the spindle, Lachesis by using both hands, Clotho with her right hand, and Atropos with her left hand.

After being assigned a lot to determine their order in the queue—the lot is gathered from Lachesis's lap and tossed to each soul by “a prophet” (προφήτης τις)—souls awaiting rebirth come forth in turn and choose their next incarnations from the wide but finite range of human and animal lives available. As the process proceeds, the pool of types diminishes, thus limiting the choices of those souls further back in the queue. Despite the intimidating presence of the goddess Necessity and her daughters and despite the spindle's inexorable spinning, the responsibility for the choice, Plato says, belongs entirely to the souls. In what would become one of Plato's most intensely discussed passages, the aforementioned prophet proclaims,

Souls of a day, this is the beginning of another round of mortal kind that ends in death. No divine spirit will select you by lot, but you will be the one to choose a divine spirit. Let the one who draws the first lot be the first to choose a life, to which he will adhere of necessity. But virtue has no master; by honoring or dishonoring it, each will have a greater or lesser share of it. The responsibility is the chooser's; god is not to be blamed. (*Rep.* 10.617e, 2:477)

The soul of Orpheus opts for the form of a swan, Agamemnon for that of an eagle, the Arcadian heroine Atalanta for the life of an athlete, and Odysseus, whose soul was the last to be drawn, for the tranquil life of an ordinary citizen. Likewise, different souls of animals choose to be reincarnated into human beings.

Once all souls have chosen their next lives, Lachesis allots them a guardian daemon as the “fulfiller of their choices” (ἀποπληρωτὴς τῶν αἰρεθέντων) (*Rep.* 10.620e). Accompanied by their daemons, the souls then go to Clotho, who ratifies their choice, and then to Atropos, who makes the choice irreversible. After passing beneath the throne of Necessity without a backward look, the souls journey in the stifling heat across the Plain of Oblivion to drink from Lethe, the river of forgetfulness, “whose waters no vessel can contain” (*Rep.* 10.621a). Having forgotten their past, they fall asleep until “a sound of thunder and a quaking of the earth” wakes them up and projects them into their new lives “like shooting stars” (*Rep.* 10.621b).

This depiction of the soul’s freedom to choose within the context of a situation presided over by the goddess Necessity and the Fates has intrigued Plato’s readers for centuries. The presence and action of these divinities in the myth clearly determine key features of the situation in which souls choose their next life but, paradoxically, do not seem to undermine the soul’s capability for self-determination. It is still possible for the soul to choose “with the mind” (σὺν νῶ) (*Rep.* 10.619b3),¹ for “virtue,” as Plato has the prophet say, “has no master.”

However, a deeper reading reveals that beneath the dense narrative layers lurks a threat to human freedom. For if souls are free, as the prophet claims, why does Plato give Necessity and the Fates such a central place in this story? To what extent can souls change their calling after Atropos has made the web of their destiny irreversible? For centuries, readers have gone back to this famous myth seeking answers, and they still today come away with new questions.

Indeed, to disentangle the elements of necessity and autonomy interwoven in Plato’s narrative is not at all easy. In Er’s story, not only does it seem impossible for souls to escape the web of Necessity after they make their choices, but it is clear that the souls arrive at the meadows predisposed toward a particular form of life as a result of their past experiences and moral behavior. For example, Orpheus chooses to become a swan in his next life after being killed by the women of Thrace in his previous life; he would rather be reincarnated into the body of an animal than born of a woman. Agamemnon decides to become an eagle because of his hatred of humans. Likewise, the soul of Atalanta, who had been the fastest mortal on earth, opts for the life of a greatly honored athlete, while Odysseus, tired of adventure, chooses the mundane life of an anonymous citizen. In each case, the soul’s choice is affected by former experiences, sometimes trying to escape them in a radically different life, sometimes seeking for a more intense or successful version of these experiences.

This has raised many questions for readers. If our identity is informed by who we were in a previous life, despite all our memories disappearing after drinking from the river Lethe, how can we ever hope to dissipate the ghost of the past? To what extent can disembodied souls choose rationally, free from the influence of the idiosyncrasies, fears, and ambitions of their past selves? Moreover, if the daemon's guardianship will not allow us to break the web woven by Atropos, can we really be said to choose who we are and who we want to be? As I said, these questions have haunted many of Plato's successors. In the *Enneads*, Plotinus rewrites the myth in philosophical terms (*Enn.* 2.3.9, 3.2.7, 3.4, and 4.3.13).² Porphyry devotes an entire treatise to it, titled "What Is in Our Power,"³ and Proclus discusses these problems widely in his *Platonic Theology* and *Commentary on the Republic*.

The difficult legacy of the myth of Er was felt far beyond antiquity and continued to exercise scholars throughout the Middle Ages and the early Renaissance in the Arabic, Byzantine, and Latin worlds. In the Latin West, the *Republic* reemerged with the first revival of Platonic studies, when the Greek émigré Manuel Chrysoloras translated it into Latin with his student Uberto Decembrio in 1402 (Garin 1955, 341–44; Hankins 1987, 149–61). This translation, a literal version containing several errors and omissions and showing very little understanding of the philosophical content (Cappelli 2010, 110; Hankins 1990a, 1: 108), was later revised by Pier Candido Decembrio, Uberto's son, between 1437 and 1440.⁴ The next signal event in the reception history of the *Republic* was the publication in 1484 of the Latin translation of the complete works of Plato, which included thirty-five dialogues and the *Platonic Letters*, by the hand of the humanist Marsilio Ficino. He embarked on the magnificent enterprise of unveiling Platonism for the contemporary Latin-speaking world in the early 1460s, under the patronage of Cosimo de' Medici. When Cosimo placed the Platonic manuscripts at his disposal,⁵ Ficino plunged into an intense program of translation and interpretation that resulted not only in the 1484 Latin version of the Platonic corpus but also the publication of detailed commentaries and *argumenta* on Plato's dialogues, translations, and commentaries on different works by the late ancient Platonists, including Plotinus, Porphyry, Iamblichus, Proclus, and Priscianus Lydus, and the writing of his own philosophical treatises, of which the *Platonic Theology* (1482) is the best known.

Ficino read Plato differently than philosophers now read him. In fact, Ficino mastered a type of interpretation that is now lost but that is nevertheless crucial for a complete understanding of Plato's dialogues—an understanding that integrates myth with philosophy and attunes them, so to speak. Given the fundamental questions on the powers and limits of

human nature that it raised and the great challenges it posed to Plato's interpreters, the myth of Er had to have a significant place in Ficino's Platonic project. Indeed, in interpreting the end of the *Republic*, Ficino found himself having to juggle the delicate relation between necessity (enforced by the Fates and by the daemon) and human freedom. The key question was this: is there a way to keep the spindle winding the thread of individual destinies while preserving the soul's power of self-determination? As an exegete deeply committed to excavating the truth of Platonism, as a philosopher in his own right interested in the possibility for humans to penetrate the natural order of things, as a priest, and, finally, as a physician concerned with how psychophysiological processes respond to celestial influences, Ficino was especially keen to unravel this knot.

Ficino discusses the myth of Er mostly in the *Platonic Theology*, in his commentary on Plato's *Phaedrus* and in the *Argumentum*, which introduces his Latin translation of the tenth book of the *Republic*, and, to a lesser extent, in his commentary on Plotinus's *Enneads* (1492). In this article, I will concentrate mostly on the *Argumentum*.⁶ Here, from many explicit and implicit references, it is clear that Ficino took Proclus's *Platonic Theology* as an authoritative hermeneutical instrument to understand the deepest meanings of Er's story.⁷ It is a shame that he could not access Proclus's own line-by-line commentary on the myth, contained in Dissertation XVI of Proclus's commentary on the *Republic*, for the codex containing Proclus's dissertations XIII–XVII (on the last three books of the *Republic*) did not reach the Latin West until the mid-seventeenth century. Ficino, however, had access to the codex that contained Dissertations I–XII (on the first seven books of the *Republic*), which was bought in 1492 by Janus Lascaris, probably in Crete, for the Medici Library in Florence, where it is now Laurenziana MS 80.9.⁸ However, Ficino had read the *Platonic Theology* both in the original Greek and in the Latin translation that Petrus Balbus Pisanus completed in 1462 for Cardinal Cusanus.⁹ A witness to Ficino's engagement with the myth of Er through Proclus is a manuscript containing Proclus's *Platonic Theology*, *Elements of Theology*, and *Elements of Physics* (now Riccardianus 70, at the Riccardiana Library in Florence), which Ficino owned and annotated. His marginal notes have been published by Henry D. Saffrey (1959).

Ficino's *Argumentum* is a short (only eleven pages in the printed edition of 1576) but dense commentary, which relies mostly on his view of the universe as a connected and interconnected organism in which different levels of life are harmoniously in touch with one another—human souls with the souls of daemons, the body with astral influences, nature and fate with providence. In the context of such a perfectly attuned world,

for Ficino, the goddess Necessity represents the Platonic Soul of the World, that is, the universal living principle that gives life to the body of the world just as the individual souls of human beings give life to their individual bodies and that features in Plato's *Timaeus*, the *Statesman*, and the *Philebus*. At the end of the *Republic*, Ficino says, Plato calls her "Necessity," "not because she uses violence against nature, or reason, but because she preserves all things in some order of her own, established by the divine craftsman" (*Argumentum*, 1434). He also describes the role of Necessity's three daughters:

Lachesis, because she is pregnant with the seeds of things and with the lots and forms of life that she sows into the souls who are on the point of descending. Then Clotho, since she unrolls the in-sown life-lots into the act of living, according to her own order, and brings them into effect. Finally, Atropos, for she preserves and protects through an unwavering course the lives which have now evolved into the act [of living] right up to their inevitable end. (*Argumentum*, 1435)10

The thrones on which they sit, he explains, represent "the firmness of the fatal order"; the white color of their dresses mirrors their nature, "inviolable and blameless at the same time"; and "the garlands on their heads testify to their power" (*Argumentum*, 1434). The movements of their hands when they turn the spindle, however, seem to conceal a much more obscure meaning. For Lachesis spins both the inner and outer circles using one hand after the other, Clotho the outer circle only with her right hand, and Atropos, likewise, the inner circle only with her left hand. The Fates' use of their hands had been the subject of Proclus's inquiry too (Proclus, *Platonic Theology*, 6.23, 2:82)—for these movements seem to point to the complex metaphysical structure holding the spinning mechanism together, the complex rhythm of the spindle weaving its story of metaphysical causality and dependence. Lachesis uses both hands, Ficino explains, "because in the beginning are contained the middle and the end," while Clotho spins the larger circle with her right hand and from the outside, for "the unfolding of life through the middle begins in an external cause and is more honorable." Finally, Atropos uses her left hand to spin the spindle from the inside, as "the unescapable end originates in a quality that is surely understood to be an inner one" and "wears thin" (*Argumentum*, 1435). "To this," Ficino goes on, "add that it creeps in silently and mostly against one's will" (*Argumentum*, 1435). For the same reason, Lachesis sings of what has been, Clotho of what is, and Atropos of what will be. Ficino here resorts to Proclus's argument that "Socrates uses the parts of time as symbols of the comprehension according to causes" (Proclus 1816, 6.23, 2:82), quoting him directly (*Argumentum*, 1435). Proclus, he says, held that, since the past contains both the present and the future, Lachesis is the noblest of the sisters. For the past "is said to have passed

away, and at some time [in the past], to have been present, and before it was present, to have been the future" (*Argumentum*, 1435).¹¹ Lachesis, therefore, "is the first effective cause, comprehending the other causes in herself" (Proclus 1816, 6.23, 2: 82).

Ficino used Proclus's interpretation of the Fates as a principle to guide to his own reading. Indeed, Proclus had described Lachesis's necessary role in sustaining the process of generation through comprising and completing the actions of her sisters. Through the movements of both hands and with the lots that she has in her lap, she links divine providence and fate. The nature of this link is at the core of Ficino's concern with Er's dream-story. However, before delving into Ficino's interpretation of the myth, a short digression on his view of human freedom of choice is warranted. His position on the vexed medieval debate about whether the soul's freedom is due more to the intellect or to the will is that the two faculties work in harmony (Albertini 2002; Edelheit 2014, 138–196; Kristeller 1965). In his *De christiana religione*, for example, he claims, "The intellect enlightens the will, the will ignites the intellect" (Ficino 1576d, 1). Surprisingly, however, in his analysis of the soul's choice of life at the end of the *Republic*, Ficino does not mention the will.

2. DIVINE PROVIDENCE AND THE SOUL'S FREE WILL

Following Plotinus, Ficino distinguishes between providence, which governs the spiritual world, and fate, which reigns in the world of generation and is ontologically subordinated to providence.¹² The drama of embodied life, for him, lies precisely in finding a way to become emancipated from fate and to ascend to the order of divine providence. For, as he writes in a letter to Giovanni Pannonio, "fate is at the service of divine providence," and "our souls can be said to be most free when they most agree with divine will" (Ficino 1576b, 872).¹³ It is precisely the harmony between providence and fate that led Ficino to his harsh criticism of positions advocating absolute determinism. His autograph marginal notes on Gemistus Pletho's *De fato* (Riccardianus 76, at the Biblioteca Riccardiana in Florence) are examples of this criticism. In this short treatise, which is a chapter of his *Laws*, Pletho claims that "if any event were to occur without being determined, either it would occur without its cause" or its cause "would be subject to no necessity" (1986, 332). Both alternatives, for Pletho, are impossible, since no event can be "uncaused" and no cause can act without being necessitated to act. Moreover, Pletho goes on, "if the future were not thus fixed, there could be no foreknowledge of either by men or even by gods" (1986, 332).

Contra Pletho, Ficino observes that both Boethius and Thomas Aquinas proved that God knows even those events produced by indeterminate

causes (Boethius 2008, 171–72; Keller 1957, 365). Aquinas argues that God’s knowledge of contingent effects (that is, effects that might or might not occur) is not affected by the indeterminacy of their cause. In the “here and now” of His eternal vision, God knows them as realized in actuality. Aquinas was an important author for Ficino, and his position on God’s knowledge of future contingents must have been the foundation from which Ficino elaborated his Platonically inspired reconciliation of divine omniscience and human freedom of moral choice. Moreover, Aquinas famously claimed that human actions are different from those of a stone, which “moves downwards,” and from those of a sheep “seeing a wolf” and judging it “as something to be shunned,” for the human being has access to the judgment of reason. “Forasmuch as man is rational,” Aquinas writes, “is it necessary that man have a free-will” (1914, 148). Being informed by reason, human freedom cannot but participate in the providential order of things—a position that, in Ficino’s eyes, must have closely resembled Plotinus’s position that we are free only when we act according to a rational desire for the true good.

However, despite the crude determinism of such an interpretation of free will, Pletho does not entirely reject it. He admits that men are somehow “masters of themselves,” “in the sense that they have within themselves their sole ruling principle, namely, their intelligence, and their other elements are ruled by it” (1986, 333). To this, Pletho adds that whether intelligence succumbs to external influences depends on its “nature and training” (1986, 134).¹⁴ Its nature, he specifies, depends on the gods, while its training depends on its own predisposition, even if the latter “cannot be implanted in a man without the attendance of a god” (1986, 334). Thus, it would seem that Pletho does not entirely deny the mind’s freedom to dispose itself autonomously and, consequently, to act autonomously (or at least to exist autonomously with respect to the elements over which it rules, that is, irrational desires). Ficino, however, takes this claim to be tantamount to assigning responsibility for the soul’s wrongdoings to God, in which case it will turn out that Pletho contradicts himself when he says that the gods are not the causes of evil (Keller 1957, 365). Certainly, Pletho’s small concession to human freedom was too embedded in his argument for external determination to appeal to (or even to be noticed by) Ficino who, to judge by his marginal notes on the *De fato*, found the view contained in this short treatise repellent.

However, Ficino’s account of free moral choice differs from that of Aquinas as well. For while Aquinas puts the locus of freedom in the interplay between the intellect and the will (for the intellect makes determinations of goodness and presents them to the will, which, in turn, wills them), Ficino is less inclined to give the intellect as important a role as the will in enabling human freedom. More precisely, although

the real agent of freedom for Ficino is *voluntas*, generally translated as “will,” his *voluntas* encompasses both the mind’s desire for God and its ability to recognize this desire as its innermost and truest aspiration. The freedom to choose between ascending to God and descending to a level of reality opposite God is not so much a matter of knowing the Good as of loving the Good. Indeed, “to know God in this life is truly impossible, but to love Him truly, in whatever way He may be known, is both possible and easy” (Ficino 2016, 52).

Admittedly, however, when discussing the souls’ choices of their next lives in Plato’s myth of Er, Ficino makes no reference to the *voluntas*. As we will see, the choice here depends entirely on the interaction between the vegetative faculty, the imagination, and reason. This is because, I believe, the *voluntas* is a specific form of will: it is a will fueled by the love of God and embodying a higher form of freedom. Love is absent in the soul’s choice of a new life, which binds the soul once more to a body. Any desire the soul might have for the body is driven by irrational impulses and, as such, is opposed to the overwhelming longing to be with God that informs the *voluntas*. It is necessary to keep this in mind to understand why Ficino’s conception of freedom of choice, otherwise necessarily connected to his idea of *voluntas*, is explained in the *Argumentum* in terms of irrational and rational choices. For in commenting on Er’s story, Ficino is not concerned with the soul that looks upward to God but with those souls that, having succumbed to the lure of material life, look downward to the body.

Like Plotinus, Porphyry, and Proclus before him, Ficino was eager to find an answer to the question of whether souls can be said to be fate-bound in the moment they choose their next incarnation. If rightly interpreted, moreover, the myth of Er could shed light on one apparently conflicting aspect of Platonic metaphysics: why do disembodied souls descend instead of enjoying immateriality for all eternity? What is the point of incarnation, if incarnation is decline? In disentangling the narrative threads of the myth, Ficino takes great efforts to explain the relationship between Necessity, Lachesis, and the soul, in order to defend virtue’s self-mastery and make embodiment Platonically intelligible.

3. EMBODIMENT AND THE CHOICE OF LIFE

In Ficino’s view, souls in their entirety are not caught up in the web woven by the spindle. Only their “irrational” part, that is, those activities attributed to the vegetative powers—nutrition, growth, generation, sleep, and metabolism—and the imagination, become meshed in the threads of fate. Reason, by which we make judgments and rational choices, remains

free. In fact, Ficino's interpretation of fate—here and elsewhere—relies on the distinction between higher and lower levels of life both on a cosmological and an individual level. The Soul of the World—Necessity—reaches down to matter through the Fates, her lowest powers.¹⁵ Likewise, following Plotinus, Ficino believes that the human soul has a higher, intellectual part that never becomes metaphysically involved with matter but that governs the body through its irrational part, which he defines in *Platonic Theology* as the *idolum* or “image of the rational soul” (2001–6, 12.4.4, 4:48).¹⁶ For, Ficino writes in *In Plotinum*, the soul is called “a human being when it emanates a certain life through the body” (1576c, 1550).¹⁷ Unlike the higher soul, the lower soul becomes trapped in the complex system of bodily activities that range from basic physiological processes to the first cognitive representations produced by the imagination—approximative and confused images of things that are still very dependent on the physicality of the object and that Ficino calls “simulacra.”¹⁸ For him, the laws of fate govern only this form of vegetative and roughly imaginative irrational life.

Intriguingly, though, and contrary to what we may think, the irrational life is not the prerogative solely of the embodied soul but exists before and beyond the body. This is the key for understanding Ficino's interpretation of the Fates in the myth of Er. The powers that in the body produce blood and the humors and that make us grow, digest food, and have sexual desires are the same that provoke the need for the body in preincarnate souls. In the *Argumentum* he writes, “It is asked for what reason here souls seem to approach Lachesis by some natural instinct” (1576a, 1436). Within the Platonic tradition, the idea of the soul's antenatal existence and reincarnation raised important questions, which seem to challenge the foundational concept of Platonic metaphysics, that is, the superiority of immaterial forms to material forms. In other words, why do disembodied souls crave the body if the body is their prison? Plato had never really given an answer to this question, but his cyclical argument in the *Phaedo* certainly points to a kind of need “to balance life and death” in the general order of nature (Allen 2002, 165). Souls are constrained to enter a new cycle “of life into death and death into life” (Allen 2002, 165); they are compelled to leave eternity for time, happiness for sorrow, mindfulness for forgetfulness.

Ficino explains in *Platonic Theology* that, when the attraction toward the body emerges in the soul, this “is impelled not externally by some kind of violence, nor as a result of its own deliberation, but by a kind of natural instinct, the sort which in this present life produces teeth, hairs, semen, and the rest, each at its appropriate time” (2001–6, 17.3.6, 6:37). Embodiment, in other words, is an inner requirement, just as the physiological processes that make the body grow and change through

time are inner requirements. This had been Plotinus's view too in "an unusual fatalistic passage" (Adamson 2008, 286n40) from *Enn.* 4.3.13: "The souls go neither willingly nor because they are sent, nor is the voluntary element in their going like deliberate choice, but like a natural spontaneous jumping or a passionate natural desire of sexual union or as some men are moved unreasoningly to noble deeds" (Plotinus 1966–88, 4:79). Hence, once it has traveled to the meadows, the soul cannot decide to turn on its heels and walk away from Lachesis, remaining in the afterlife a little longer or forever.

As mentioned above, those souls who have lived in accordance with the most excellent part of their nature and have become united with the divine are able to break the pattern of birth-death-rebirth, escaping the cycle of reincarnation and, thus, disengaging themselves from the mesh of fate. However, those souls who did not live up to their innate excellence and, as a consequence, find themselves standing in front of Necessity's daughters, have no choice but to choose: more precisely, not only to choose but to long for choosing. This, Ficino believes, is the coercive aspect of choice, where Necessity makes herself manifest, that is, in the fact that it is impossible for the soul not to make a choice. However, once the lots have been cast from Lachesis's lap and the paradigms of lives laid on the ground, the soul becomes free to select its next incarnation among the various possibilities on offer:

For even if the choice of a new life, both now and in the past, occurs by fate (whether by communal or personal fate), the choice of this or that particular life in the proper sense, arises from conscious deliberation. (*Argumentum*, 1436)

Ficino stresses the difference between lots (κλήροι, *sortes*), which the prophet casts (ρίπτει, *fundit*) in front of the soul and which the soul is impelled to pick up by a natural instinct, and the models of life (βίων παραδείγματα, *exempla vitarum*), which the prophet places in front of souls (τίθησιν εἰς τὸ πρόσθεν σφῶν, *coram ipsis disponit*) (Plato, *Rep.* 10.618a).¹⁹ The reason is that, he explains, "the lots belong to the vegetative powers," while "the models belong to the imaginations" (*Argumentum*, 1436). Ficino goes on:

Certainly, at the time when in this faculty [that is, the vegetative power] some such seeds of future life grow more powerful than others, images and contrivances of a correlative life flood into the imagination, and the emotions begin to boil up—just as with us a joyous imagination accompanies a corporal state that is sanguine, whereas an angry imagination accompanies a choleric state, a sad imagination a melancholic state, and a libidinous imagination accompanies a phlegmatic one. Fatal necessity advances thus far. (*Argumentum*, 1436)

However, after this stage, Necessity steps aside, letting reason decide what to do with those impulses, images, and passions that have been aroused by the picking up of the lots and the sight of the models of life. By reasoning (*ratiocinatio*), judging (*consilium*), and choosing (*electio*), reason examines the life presented to it by the forms and passions of the imagination and decides whether to approve or reject it:

If, upon examination, reason rejects the first form of life brought before its eyes by the imagination, a better one will immediately present itself, and after that, yet another. (*Argumentum*, 1436)

Ficino did not comment on the single choices made by the souls in the myth of Er, for to attract the reader's attention to reincarnation into animal bodies would have come with the risk of sympathizing with Plato's most heterodox belief, something extremely unwise for one in his position. In fact, Ficino was obsessed with showing that Plato did not believe in such a "ridiculous old wives' tale."²⁰ Thus, even though in the *Republic* transmigration is introduced to support Plato's anthropology and eschatology, Ficino concludes the *Argumentum* by reassuring readers that Plato "surely advises us to interpret the topic entirely allegorically" (1438). What Plato really means, he explains, is not that rational souls migrate into the life of an animal (*in vitam bruti*) but that they move into an animal life (*in vitam brutam*) (*Argumentum*, 1438), that is, they make themselves somehow similar to beasts.

However, had Ficino commented on the choices made by the characters mentioned by Er, he would have described the selection process in terms of an ordered interaction between the faculties of the soul. Let us imagine the choice made by Agamemnon's soul according to Ficino's scheme "vegetative faculty/imagination/reason." Agamemnon appears before Lachesis driven by a natural instinct to pick up one of the available lots to satisfy his craving for incarnate life. At the sight of the different models presented to him, his imagination is stirred, evoking emotions connected with his life in the human world. A life of honor and power arouses memories of his struggle to maintain his status as the most powerful prince in Greece; that of a private citizen still carries the fear of betrayal and loss; that of a dog, we may suppose, provokes a feeling of shame at being downgraded to live as the most submissive animal of all. Finally, the life of an eagle strikes the king's imagination with images of power and dominion, yet free from the dangers and sorrows of political power, married life, and fatherhood. In Ficino's view, this tumultuous succession of natural impulses and emotions in Agamemnon's preincarnate soul is driven by fate, inasmuch as it happens by nature and not by deliberation. However, once reason is used to examine the various life models presented and Agamemnon rejects all of them in

favor of the life of the eagle, his soul is free, and he is responsible for the consequences of his choice.

Ficino's interpretation of the myth of Er is rooted in his view of human nature as a complex unity made up of different and even opposing dimensions, in which the imagination has a key role in mediating between the vegetative and the rational levels. As a physician, he is aware of the original tendency of life for self-preservation and its need to reach outside itself to generate new life through reproduction. As a philosopher, he long examined and discussed the ability of reason to make free choices and to take full responsibility for the ways it governs its biological and emotional dimensions. Finally, as a theologian, he believed that the original tendency of life to self-preservation—embedded in nature, and accounting for all the teleological processes occurring in the material universe—is perfectly attuned to the rhythm through which divine providence works in the world.

The figure of the “prophet” is essential to understanding this idea of attunement and interconnectivity.²¹ Ficino claims that Plato introduces the prophet to make clear how providence works on two fronts: he makes sure that the plan of God is fulfilled and that our choices are truly our own. More precisely, the speech that the prophet addresses to souls, Ficino says, signifies two things: one is “the universal and primal influence of providence on the soul”; the other is the moment at which the “concurrence” (*concursum*, here understood in theological terms as the cooperation of divine and natural causes) takes place, for which “souls are brought where universal fate brings them” (*Argumentum*, 1436). The fact that the prophet arranges the souls in order before they receive the lots from Lachesis's lap (*Rep.* 10.617d) confirms that the choice happens because of both the favor of providence and the concurrence between divine and human acts (*Argumentum*, 1436). The prophet, hence, works with Lachesis in assuring a perfect accord between providence and fate. He doesn't compel the soul but inspires her:

This inspiration of providence is given the name of prophet. For by means of a kind of light of judgement, she presages to reason that it has a free power of deliberation and choice, regardless of what eventuates from its imprudent choosing. The prophet is also said to cast the lots and to display the models of life, not only because the influence of divine providence in some way ratifies what has been destined, but because she displays the fatal lots and examples to the examination and judgement of reason. (*Argumentum*, 1436)

The cycle of life, driven by fate, reflects and executes the laws of providence, while reason, free and sovereign, is able to decode these laws and to be inspired by them. What is more, the soul can ascend to the level

of intellectual contemplation, escaping “celestial fate” and following the guidance of “both the supercelestial providence of God and the freedom of the mind” (Ficino 1576b, 776).²² In the unbroken vision of the divine, the soul’s desires coincide with the providential design. Human freedom, now exerted above fate, is enhanced. By contrast, those souls who are still journeying through life and death are confined by the limits imposed on them by the vegetative and imaginative dimensions of incarnated life, whose phantom is carried along in the disembodied state. However, even in the cyclic cosmic pattern that represents “the mystery of souls who return from heaven to earth and vice-versa” (*Argumentum*, 1436), reason is the guarantor of the soul’s freedom. In other words, even when we are entangled in the net of bodily life and fate, reason can make us free. Because of reason, we stay responsible for the way we relate to higher (the divine, the forms, and the intellect) and lower (the body, the vegetative faculty, and the imagination) realities, Ficino asserts in *Platonic Theology*:

Through the mind [we are joined] to providence, through the idolum to fate, and through our single nature to universal nature—yet through the reason we are entirely a law unto ourselves, and like free beings we can pursue now these faculties and now those. (2001–6, 13.2.19, 4:143)

In the cosmic cycle, reason’s own judgment and choice are to be blamed for our downfall and praised for our ascent. In the ascent, Ficino writes in the *Commentary on Plotinus*, the mind will realize that the capability for divine contemplation is “hers” and that it “has inborn in it the forms of things to be contemplated and is itself these forms” (2017, 4:491). In other words, we have an innate ability to correct and perfect our pitch sensitivity to perceive the absolute and perpetual harmony between providence and fate, who sing perhaps not the same melody but in the same key. For Necessity, that is, the Soul of the World, “as though a worldly Apollo, sings in nature and plucks his lyre in the heaven” (2017, 5:383). If anyone examines the continuity and arrangement of the song sung in nature, Ficino says, “he will immediately perceive the heavenly sounds in that continuity, and will be as though now hearing them” (2017, 5:383).

4. CONCLUSION

Attunement is a fundamental concept underlying Ficino’s view of providence, fate, and human freedom and his interpretation of the myth of Er. For, in his philosophical cosmology, providence and fate are in perfect harmony. “All things that come about according to fate,” he says in the *Commentary on Plotinus*, “come about according to providence, although providence accomplishes many things in addition which are not included within the limits of fate” (2017, 4:269). He further explains that “fate depends on providence in a manner not dissimilar to that in

which heat depends on light,” where the things accomplished by heat “are also accomplished by the light although the reverse is not the case, for wonderful powers that are not in the heat lie hidden in the light” (2017, 4:269). Individual souls become truly free when they become able to perceive this correspondence and attune themselves to the harmony of the Soul of the World’s music, like singers who imitate melodies or produce concordant notes or like dancers adjusting their choreography to the music they are performing:

There exists therefore in the vegetative faculty of our soul a fate appropriate to it and, folded within this, a series of future events, conforming in form, mode, and time to the fates of the celestial souls and of the World-Soul. And just as the seed of any plant in its own time swells into the shapes proper to it, and appears to change of its own accord in harmony with the universal nature of spring time encouraging it to the same end, just so do souls through their own nature bring forth their own lives in accordance with their fate at that time when universal fate summons them to these same lives. As a consequence of this, the chorus of souls, through its own dancing manoeuvres and through the diversity of its various dancers, imitates the chant of fate and its sound. I would like the chant to be understood as [taking place] in the celestial souls, the sound in the spheres, and the dance within us. (*Argumentum*, 1436)23

The image of the dance is one that Ficino uses often to describe how the different parts of the universe are attuned to one another (see, for example, Ficino 2017, 4:321). The premodern universe is deeply imbued with the divine, and, in Plato, Ficino found a key to understanding the system of signs and relationships that, if interpreted correctly, reveal the hand of providence writing the perfectly timed chapters of the soul’s story. Within this story, the three Fates enforce the elements of necessity, such as loss, forgetfulness, and death (all synonyms in Ficino’s Platonic hermeneutics), but which, in his view, pose no harm to human freedom. For through reason and the intellect, the soul is able to understand and accept loss, reverse forgetfulness, and even rejoice in death as true liberation from fate.

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NOTES

1. See Wilberding 2013, 88.
2. See Adamson 2008.

3. Greenbaum 2015, 284–86, 394; and 2018; Johnson 2013, 37–38; and Wilberding 2013.

4. Bottoni 1984; Gusmini 2012; Hankins 1990a, 2:530–95; Zaccaria 1959; and Zaggia 1993.

5. Ficino thanks Cosimo for the Platonic manuscripts in a letter dated September 4, 1462. This letter is printed in Hankins 1990b, 159–60, and in Kristeller 1937, 2:87–88. See Corrias 2017, 100; Della Torre 1902, 537–38; Field 2002, 374; and Kristeller 1966, 43. On Ficino and Cosimo, see Robichaud 2018, 80–95.

6. All translations from this work are mine.

7. On Ficino’s use of Proclus’s *Elements of Theology*, see Robichaud 2016, especially 63–65. On Ficino’s reception of Proclus in general, see Allen 1982, 1994, 2014, and 2015; Copenhaver 1988; Megna 2003 and 2004; Robichaud 2016 and 2017; Sanzotta 2014; and Steel 2013.

8. Allen 1994, 38, and 2014, 359; Gentile 1984.

9. Allen 2014, 357, and 2015, 184–85; Robichaud, 2016, 52; and Saffrey, 1979.

10. See Ficino 2001–6, 6:38, where Lachesis is defined “sortitia,” that is, she who appoints the lots; Clotho “revolutrix,” that is, she who revolves; and Atropos “inconvertibilis,” that is, she who is irrevocable.

11. See Proclus 1816, 6.23, 2:82: “For the past was once the future, and the present, but the future is not yet the past, but has the whole of its essence in existing in some after time.”

12. More precisely, Ficino famously distinguishes between three orders: providence, which governs the supercelestial realm; fate, the law of the celestial realm; and nature, which rules over matter. However, the complex interaction between these three orders is beyond the scope of this article. On the topic see, among others, Allen 1994, 107–9; Gersh 2017, civ–cix); Heitzman 1936; Kristeller 1943, 368–88; and Trinkaus 1970, 2:476–78.

13. Allen 1994, 109n8; and Dini 2003, 26.

14. I have changed Woodhouse’s translation of φύσις as “character” into “nature.”

15. For the role of the Soul of the World in producing life in the natural world, see Copenhaver 2015, 55–68.

16. Giglioni 2011, 28.

17. See also Ficino 2001–6, 13.2.11, 4:135: “This is the ruler of the body: it nourishes the body in the body, perceives things corporeal through the body, and moves and rules the body through and in space”; and Ficino 2017, 5:436): “The soul is bound to the body as though with two ligatures, one of these being a tendency toward soul: that is, its life-giving act springing forth toward the body, the other being an inclination toward the body: namely, the *quasi*-vital

quality itself that is infused into the body by means of the life-giving act." On this passage, see Gersh 2018, 205.

18. Allen 1989; Giglioni 2010; Heitzman 1935; and Kristeller 1943, 234–37, 360–64, and 367–69.

19. Ficino's Latin translation is in Plato 1548, 455.

20. See *Argumentum*, 1438; Allen 1995b, 437–39, and 2007; Celenza 1999, 684–89; Hankins 1990, 1:358 and 2005, 12; Ogren 2004 and 2005.

21. The importance of "attunement" for Platonism can be traced back to Plato's *Phaedo* 85e–86d and 91c–95a. See especially Bostock 1986, 122–34.

22. See Allen 1994, 109n7.

23. For the Plotinian inspiration in this passage, see Plotinus 1966–88, IV.3.13, 4:79.

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